

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AKIIKI ASIIMWE****FIRST NAME: DEOGRATIAS****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: PERIOD 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

Our plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 4%

The author used the following software (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D-PERIOD 6

1. In the EUCLID writing system, the following are the recommended systematic referencing forms in writing references.

- Form of referencing if it is consistent and follows the Chicago format
- Form of referencing if it is strict in its format and consistent throughout the paper¹**
- Form of referencing that is in agreement with the Turabian format of citation
- Form of citation that is in strict format and consistent with Chicago

¹ Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 11.

2. In the modern writing experience, researchers have resorted to adopting sources of information without crediting the author of that source of information. This situation is known as;

- Pragmatism
- Referencing
- Quotation
- Plagiarism²**

3. In this book, we use research in a specific way, which means a process of systematic inquiry to answer a question that the researcher and others want to solve. At what point can one declare the research process complete?

- When the researcher analyses and interprets data
- When the researcher presents their findings to the supervisor
- When the researcher shares his findings and conclusions with others³**
- When the researcher collects data from the respondents

4. The researcher has to plan our presentation before considering a discussion and gaining experience in research.

- When the researcher plans a presentation, they get immediate feedback⁴**
- When the researcher plans a presentation, one gets answers constantly

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 11.

³ Turabian L. Kate, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth edition (London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 30.

⁴ Ibid., 130.

- The researcher plans the presentation well to understand the process better
 - When the researcher plans the presentation well, they present a better
5. Several reasons prompt them to cite our sources in research. The following are the reasons;
- To give credit.
 - To reassure readers about the accuracy of our r facts
 - To show readers the research tradition that informs our work
 - To help researchers follow or extend their research⁵**
6. In writing research, there are vital factors to consider when using abbreviations; the researcher should remember that;
- The researcher uses abbreviations only sparingly⁶**
 - The researcher uses abbreviations continuously in the work
 - The researcher only abbreviates where expected
 - The researcher includes all forms of abbreviations vigorously
7. On the doctoral thesis, the PhD student has to understand the components of dissertation research. They include the following.
- Dissertation concept paper
 - Dissertation prospectus

⁵ Turabian, 30.

⁶ Ibid., 353.

Dissertation

Dissertation superscript⁷

8. From the qualitative and quantitative perspective, the researcher uses either qualitative or quantitative design. The researcher uses either research questions or research hypotheses in the design. The researcher will use a hypothesis in its totality because ⁸,

It tests differences or relationships among variables tested in the dissertation research.

It tests the similarities between the variables that questions cannot answer.

It tests the relationships between two or more scholarly documents in research.

A null hypothesis assumes that there are no differences among variables

9. In some instances, academic writers are to use ellipsis in the sentence. Given its usage, the researcher should pay attention to all the details that govern their use. The following is the most accurate way to use it;

No further full stop at the end of the ellipsis⁹

There is no need for a complete stop at the beginning of the ellipsis

There is a complete stop at the end of the ellipsis

There is both an ellipsis and a complete stop at the end of the ellipsis

⁷ Sampson P. James, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 9-10.

⁸ Ibid., 34.

⁹ European Union. *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission, second edition* (European Union, 2021), 8.

10. Proper use of nouns is a paramount aspect of writing and presenting any document.

Under what circumstances does a collective noun take a singular?

- Collective nouns are singular when the emphasis is on individual members.
- Collective nouns take the singular when the emphasis is on the whole entity.¹⁰**
- Collective nouns take a singular when the emphasis is on a partial entity
- Collective nouns do not take any emphasis but are, instead, used in a sentence

¹⁰ European Union, 51.

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